

THERMAL ENERGY STORAGE SYSTEMS

FOR ENERGY EFFICIENT BUILDINGS

PROJECT ID

PROJECT NAME

Thermal Energy Storage Systems for Energy Efficient Buildings. An integrated solution for residential building energy storage by solar and geothermal resources

PROJECT ACRONYM

TESSe2b

DURATION

4 years

BUDGET

€ 4.311.700

PROGRAM

EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020 RESEARCH AND INNOVATION WORK PROGRAMME 2014 - 2015

TOPIC

EeB-06-2015 - Integrated solutions of thermal energy storage for building applications

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER

680 555

EXPECTED REDUCTION IN BUILDING
ENERGY CONSUMPTION 25-30%

THE ESTIMATED PAYBACK PERIOD
IS EXPECTED TO REACH
8-9 YEARS

CONSORTIUM

- 1 IPS, Polytechnic Institute of Setubal | PORTUGAL (**COORDINATOR**)
- 2 CRES, Center for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving | GREECE
- 3 NKUA, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens | GREECE
- 4 GEOTEAM, Geoteam Technical Office for Hydrogeology, Geothermal Energy and Environment | AUSTRIA
- 5 UOI, University of Ioannina | GREECE
- 6 SGGW, Warsaw University of Life Sciences | POLAND
- 7 RUB, Ruhr University of Bochum | GERMANY
- 8 ECOSERVEIS, Association ECOSERVEIS | SPAIN
- 9 PCM, Phase Change Material Products Ltd | UNITED KINGDOM
- 10 Z&X, Z&X Mechanical Installations Ltd | CYPRUS

TESSE2B PARTNERS

WHAT_ TESSE²B PROJECT

TESSe2b project develops an integrated solution for residential buildings energy storage, using solar and geothermal energy, with the purpose of correcting the mismatch that often occurs between the supply and demand of energy in residential buildings. TESSe2b designs, develops, validates and demonstrates a modular and low cost thermal storage technology based on Phase Change Material (PCM) to provide domestic hot water (DHW), space heating and cooling.

The solution integrates compact Thermal Energy Storage (TES) PCM Tanks with solar collectors and highly efficient geothermal heat pumps with enhanced PCM borehole heat exchangers (BHEs). To optimize the energetic and economic performance of the entire system, TESse2b solution is managed by an advanced energy smart self-learning control system specially developed for this application.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- Select and characterize PCMs to optimize the design and performance for high efficiency PCM TES Tanks and enhanced PCM borehole heat exchangers.
- Exploit nanotechnology to develop new nanoparticles enhanced paraffin PCM (NEPCM).
- Design, optimize and develop compact modular TES units, including a high performance Heat Exchanger (HE).
- Develop a thin film coating to protect the TES tanks HE against the salt-hydrates corrosivity.
- Develop a smart self-learning control system for efficient TESS_e2b operation and integration into a robust working prototype.
- Design an effective exploitation strategy and business plan to demonstrate the overall benefits of TESS_e2b solution.

EXPECTED RESULTS

- Reduce the buildings net energy consumption in 25-30% and its associated CO₂ emissions.
- Achieve a payback period of 8-9 years.
- Increase the share of Removable Energy Sources in the building domestic sector.
- Contribute for the electric grid flexibility.

ENVIRONMENTALLY FRIENDLY, LOW COST AND SAFE

- Reduction of the environmental impact of residential buildings.
- Contribution to meet the EU's environmental objectives.
- Capability of simple and cost effective modernization of existing buildings and integration into new buildings.

HOW_ WORK PLAN

TESSE²B WORK PACKAGES

SYSTEM LAYOUT

TESSe2b solution has TES tanks that store energy at three different levels, according to the specific application. The Cold storage tanks for residential space cooling, the Hot storage tanks for residential space heating and a TES tank that operate at a high temperature to produce DHW. The system layout exemplifies the general structure of the TESSe2b solution implemented in the Spanish demosite, with the solar collectors, one DHW tank, four Hot TES tanks, two Cold TES tanks and the geothermal heat pump with PCM enhanced BHEs. Each demosite has a customized solution for its specific needs, as will all the buildings fitted with the TESSe2b solution.

SPAIN DEMOSITE SYSTEM LAYOUT

PHASE CHANGE MATERIALS

Comparatively to conventional sensible heat storage technology, the use of PCMs provides higher heat storage capacity and more isothermal behavior during charging and discharging. The key parameter to select a PCM for an application is its freezing/melting temperature, so this temperature must be within a range defined by the application requirements.

- ✓ PCM STORES AS MUCH ENERGY AS A WATER ΔT OF 40K
- ✓ SENSIBLE HEAT LEADS TO INCREASED HEAT LOSSES TO SURROUNDINGS
- ✓ WITH PCM YOU CAN “SELECT” A PHASE CHANGE TEMPERATURE

SENSIBLE HEAT VS LATENT HEAT

However, in the selection process of a PCM many other aspects must to be considered, such as: phase transition temperature range; heat capacity; volumetric latent heat; thermal conductivity; reversible freezing/melting cycle; life-time; compatibility with other materials (plastics and metals); toxicity; flammability; cost; availability on the market; etc.

TESSe2b project developed and tested different solutions to operate with hydrated salts and organic based PCMs, and the final option fell on the organic base PCMs. For the TES tanks were selected three paraffins that store thermal energy at three different temperature levels according with the application: A9 for the Cold energy storage tanks, A44 for the Hot energy storage tanks and A53 for the DHW tanks.

The PCMs selection, to be integrated into the BHEs, was made based on how to best take advantage of the ground temperature. For Austria and Spain was selected a PCM with a freezing/melting point three Celsius degrees lower than the ground temperature to stabilize the borehole temperature over the heating season. On the contrary, for the Cyprus demosite was selected a PCM with a freezing/melting point three Celsius degrees above the ground temperature to stabilize the borehole temperature during the cooling season.

PCM	APPLICATION	NOMINAL FREEZING/MELTING TEMPERATURE (°C)	LATENT ENTHALPY (kJ/kg)
PARAFFIN WAX A9	COLD TES TANKS AUSTRIA BHES	9	185
PARAFFIN WAX A12	SPAIN BHES	12	214
PARAFFIN WAX A28	CYPRUS BHES	28	270
PARAFFIN WAX A44	HOT TES TANKS	44	268
PARAFFIN WAX A53	DHW STORAGE TANKS	53	238

PCM THERMAL ENERGY STORAGE TANKS

The TESse2b tanks were designed in a compact and modular manner for an easy integration into the buildings. The tanks design was done according to the European standards and supported by computational Finite Element Analysis (FEA). The final design consists in a polypropylene tank reinforced by five horizontal ribs and three steel bars. Inside each tank, there are high performance tubes and fins HE designed to achieve the required heat transfer rate between the PCM and the heat carrier fluid during the TES tanks operation (charge/discharge process).

The HE design was supported by CFD simulations and laboratorial experimental tests. The modular design of the tanks allows easily fit the total energy storage capacity of the system to each building, selecting the appropriate number of tanks. The internal volume of each tank is approximately 180 L (PCM plus HE).

TES TANK

PCM ENHANCED BHEs FOR GROUND SOURCE HEAT PUMP

Another innovation of TESSe2b project is the development of a BHE that can also be used for the storage of thermal energy, thus supporting the system in order to increase its performance in the heating and cooling mode. During the operation of the heat pump in the heating mode, the temperature of the heat carrier fluid within the BHE will decrease, and during the cooling it will increase.

As the heat transfer in the ground is mainly conductive and its thermal diffusivity is low, this leads to a much slower ground thermal response than the heat pump requirements, resulting in thermal waves being transmitted into the ground, which penalize the performance of GSHP systems. Adding PCMs into the boreholes is regarded as an effective mean to store thermal energy in the BHEs and improves the performance of GSHP systems. The thermal energy stored into the PCMs will smooth the ground thermal wave generated by the GSHP operation and enhance the SPF (seasonal performance factor) of the system. Depending on the PCM phase change temperature this can be applied to the heating or cooling mode.

EXPECTED IMPACT OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF PCMS INTO THE BOREHOLES
OVER THE HEATING SEASON (GREEN LINE)

SMART CONTROL SYSTEM

Another of the major TESSe2b innovations is the use of self-learning management system that will use an algorithm combining a prototype model, a user profile database, weather forecasting and multi-variable controls.

This adapts the system operation to the building user schedule and with weather forecasting to take maximum advantage of available energy that is or is going to be stored while taking advantage of lower energy tariffs during night time.

The control system will be managed based on the input of an array of sensors and actuators that will automatically change the system mode of operation according to the needs of the building.

CONTROL SYSTEM LAYOUT AND ITS INTERACTIONS

WHERE_ DEMONSTRATION SITES

Aiming to evaluate the system's integration into building space, a demonstration and on-site monitoring evaluation of TESSe2b solution will be held in three pilot sites to access its impact in different climates and provide evidence about its overall technical and economic feasibility.

SPAIN

LOCATION

CALONGE DE SEGARRA, BARCELONA REGION

CLIMATE

MEDITERRANEAN, (BSK)

DESIGN TEMPERATURES

5 °C | 28 °C

THE BUILDING

2 FLOORS, SINGLE FAMILY HOUSE.

AUSTRIA

LOCATION

KAPFENBERG, GRAZ REGION

CLIMATE

CONTINENTAL, (DFB)

DESIGN TEMPERATURES

-5 °C | 24 °C

THE BUILDING

1 FLOOR, SINGLE FAMILY HOUSE.

CYPRUS

LOCATION

MILIOU VILLAGE, PAFOS REGION

CLIMATE

MEDITERRANEAN, (CSA)

DESIGN TEMPERATURES

7 °C | 30 °C

THE BUILDING

2 FLOORS, SINGLE FAMILY HOUSE.

DEMOSITE CHARACTERISTICS

DEMOSITE	AUSTRIA	CYPRUS	SPAIN
AREA (m ²)	321	221	138
HEATING CAPACITY (kW)	14,4	17,0	12,2
COOLING CAPACITY (kW)	4,67	18,6	4,92
HEATING ANNUAL NEEDS (kWh/m ²)	55,1	45,3	63,9
COOLING ANNUAL NEEDS (kWh/m ²)	8,67	69,9	6,85
SOLAR COLLECTORS AREA (m ²)	13,6	23,5	23,5
HOT PCM TANKS	3	3	4
COLD PCM TANKS	*	3	3
DHW TANK	1	1	1
SOLAR FRACTION HEATING	11,8%	30,5%	33,5%
INCREASE OF SOLAR FRACTION DUE TO THE PCM	8,2%	27,0%	31,0%
SOLAR FRACTION HEATING+DHW	20,9%	42,3%	47,0%

* FREE-COOLING, RED ESTIMATED VALUES

WHO_ STAKEHOLDERS AND TARGET APPLICATIONS FIELDS

STAKEHOLDERS

- Industry.
- Installers.
- Equipment manufactures.
- End users (individuals/ household members).
- Energy consultants and agencies.
- Professionals related to building construction and market (architects, constructors, engineers, real estate managers).

TARGET APPLICATION

- Single-dwelling houses.

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“THIS BROCHURE PRESENTS THE PROJECT STATUS OF MARCH 2019.”

European
Commission

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